

Interval Valued Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract: Within this paper, we present and research the definition of interval valued neutrosophic topological space along with interval valued neutrosophic finer and interval valued neutrosophic coarser topologies. We also describe interval valued neutrosophic interior and closer of an interval valued neutrosophic set. Interval valued neutrosophic subspace topology also studied. Some examples and theorems are presented concerning this concept.

Keywords: Interval valued neutrosophic topology, Interval valued neutrosophic subspace topology

1. Introduction

The notion of fuzzy set has invaded almost all branches of mathematics since its introduction by Zadeh[20]. Fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic has been applied in many real applications to handle uncertainly fuzzy set theory is very successful in handling uncertainties arising from vagueness or partial belongingness of an element in a set, it cannot model all type of uncertainties pre – veiling in different real physical problems such as problems involving incomplete information. Turksen [18] introduced the idea of interval valued fuzzy sets.

Later, Atanassov[10] introduced the concept generalization of fuzzy set, which is known as intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets take into account both the degree of membership and non – membership. Further, intuitionistic fuzzy sets were extended to the interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets[11]. The interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy set uses a pair of interval $[t^-, t^+]$, $0 \leq t^- \leq t^+ \leq 1$ and $[f^-, f^+]$, $0 \leq f^- \leq f^+ \leq 1$ with $t^+ + f^+ \leq 1$, to describe the degree of true belief and false belief. Because of the restriction that $t^+ + f^+ \leq 1$, intuitionistic fuzzy sets and interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets can only handle incomplete information not the indeterminate information and inconsistent information which exists commonly in belief systems.

As a generalization of fuzzy set and intuitionistic fuzzy set, neutrosophic set have been introduced and developed by F. Smaramdache[15,16 & 17]. It is a logic in which each proposition is calculated to have degree of truth(T), a degree of indeterminacy(I) and a degree of falsity(F). Smarandache's neutrosophic concept have wide range of real applications for many fields of

[1,2,3,4,5,6,7 & 8] information system, computer science, artificial intelligence, applied mathematics, decision making, mechanics, electrical and electronics, medicine and management science etc.

Salama, Albloe[14] proposed the concept of neutrosophic topological space. Later, Wang, Smarandache, Zhang and Sunderraman introduced the notion of interval valued neutrosophic set[19]. An interval valued neutrosophic set A defined on X , $x = x(T, I, F) \in A$ with T, I and F being the subinterval of $[0,1]$. Lupianez discusses the relation between interval value neutrosophic sets and topology [12]

The purpose of this article is to propose the idea of interval valued neutrosophic topological space and discuss the some of the basic properties.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1[19] Let X be a space of points (objects), with a generic element in X denoted by x . An interval valued neutrosophic set(INS) A in X is characterized by truth – membership function T_A , indeterminacy – membership function I_A and falsity – membership function F_A . For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \subseteq [0,1]$.

Example 2.2[19] Suppose, $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3\}$. The strength is x_1 , the trust is x_2 and the price is x_3 . The x_1, x_2 and x_3 values are given in $[0,1]$. They're obtained from some domain experts ' questionnaire, their choice could be degree of goodness, degree of indeterminacy, and degree of poorness. A and B are the interval neutrosophic sets of X define by $A = <$
 $\frac{[0.2,0.4],[0.3,0.5],[0.3,0.5]}{x_1}, \frac{[0.5,0.7],[0.0,0.2],[0.2,0.3]}{x_2}, \frac{[0.6,0.8],[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.3]}{x_3} >$ $B = <$
 $\frac{[0.5,0.7],[0.1,0.3],[0.1,0.3]}{x_1}, \frac{[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.4],[0.5,0.8]}{x_2}, \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.0,1],[0.3,0.4]}{x_3} >$

Definition 2.3[19] An interval neutrosophic set A is empty if and only if its $\inf T_A(x) = \sup T_A(x) = 0$, $\inf I_A(x) = \sup I_A(x) = 1$ and $\inf F_A(x) = \sup F_A(x) = 0$, for all x in X .

Definition 2.4(Containment) [19] An interval neutrosophic set A is contained in the other interval neutrosophic set B , $A \subseteq B$, if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} \inf T_A(x) &\leq \inf T_B(x), \sup T_A(x) \leq \sup T_B(x) \\ \inf I_A(x) &\geq \inf I_B(x), \sup I_A(x) \geq \sup I_B(x) \\ \inf F_A(x) &\geq \inf F_B(x), \sup F_A(x) \geq \sup F_B(x) \end{aligned}$$

for all x in X .

Definition 2.5[19] Two interval neutrosophic sets A and B are equal, written as $A = B$, if and only if $A \subseteq B$ and $B \subseteq A$. Let $0_N = < 0,1,1 >$ and $1_N = < 1,0,0 >$.

Definition 2.6[19] The complement of an interval neutrosophic set A is denoted by \bar{A} and is defined by $T_{\bar{A}}(x) = F_A(x)$; $\inf I_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1 - \sup I_A(x)$; $\sup I_{\bar{A}}(x) = 1 - \inf I_A(x)$; $F_{\bar{A}}(x) = T_A(x)$ for all x in X .

Example 2.7[19] Let A be the interval neutrosophic set defined in Example 2.3, then $\bar{A} = <$
 $\frac{[0.3,0.5],[0.5,0.7],[0.3,0.4]}{x_1}, \frac{[0.2,0.3],[0.8,0],[0.5,0.7]}{x_2}, \frac{[0.2,0.3],[0.7,0.8],[0.6,0.8]}{x_3} >$

Definition 2.8 (Intersection) [19] The intersection of two interval neutrosophic sets A and B is an interval neutrosophic set $C = A \cap B$, whose truth-membership, indeterminacy – membership and false – membership are related to those of A and B by

$$\begin{aligned} \inf T_C(x) &= \min(\inf T_A(x), \inf T_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \min(\sup T_A(x), \sup T_B(x)) \\ \inf I_C(x) &= \max(\inf I_A(x), \inf I_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \max(\sup I_A(x), \sup I_B(x)) \\ \inf F_C(x) &= \max(\inf F_A(x), \inf F_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \max(\sup F_A(x), \sup F_B(x)) \end{aligned}$$

for all x in X .

Example 2.9[19] Let A and B be the interval neutrosophic sets defined in Example 2.3, then $A \cap B =$

$$\left\langle \frac{[0.2,0.4],[0.3,0.5],[0.3,0.5]}{x_1}, \frac{[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.4],[0.5,0.8]}{x_2}, \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.2,0.3],[0.3,0.4]}{x_3} \right\rangle.$$

Theorem 2.10[19] $A \cap B$ is the largest interval neutrosophic set contained in both A and B .

Definition 2.11(Union) [19] The union of two interval neutrosophic sets A and B is an interval neutrosophic set C , written as $C = A \cup B$, whose truth – membership, indeterminacy – membership and false membership are related to those of A and B by

$$\begin{aligned} \inf T_C(x) &= \max(\inf T_A(x), \inf T_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \max(\sup T_A(x), \sup T_B(x)) \\ \inf I_C(x) &= \min(\inf I_A(x), \inf I_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \min(\sup I_A(x), \sup I_B(x)) \\ \inf F_C(x) &= \min(\inf F_A(x), \inf F_B(x)), & \sup T_C(x) &= \min(\sup F_A(x), \sup F_B(x)) \end{aligned}$$

for all x in X .

Example 2.12[19] Let A and B be the interval neutrosophic sets defined in Example 2.3, then $A \cup B =$

$$\left\langle \frac{[0.5,0.7],[0.1,0.3],[0.1,0.3]}{x_1}, \frac{[0.5,0.7],[0,0.2],[0.2,0.3]}{x_2}, \frac{[0.6,0.8],[0,0.1],[0.2,0.3]}{x_3} \right\rangle.$$

Theorem 2.13[19] $A \cup B$ is the smallest interval neutrosophic set containing both A and B .

3. Interval Valued Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

With some examples and results, we give the concept of interval valued neutrosophic topological spaces.

Definition 3.1 An interval valued neutrosophic topological space of interval valued neutrosophic set (In short IVN topological space) is a pair (X, τ_N) where X is a nonempty set and τ_N is a family of IVN sets on X satisfying the following axioms:

1. $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$
2. $A, B \in \tau_N \Rightarrow A \cap B \in \tau_N$
3. $A_i \in \tau_N, i \in I \Rightarrow \cup_{i \in I} A_i \in \tau_N$

τ_N is called an interval valued neutrosophic topology on X . τ_N members are called interval valued neutrosophic open sets (In Short IVN open sets).

Example 3.2 Assume that $X = \{a, b\}$. Here a is denoted by quality of Computers, b is denoted by Price of Computers. The value of a and b are in $[0,1]$. These are collected from some domain expects questionnaire; their choices could be degree of excellence, degree of indeterminacy, degree of poorness. The IVN set are

$0_N = \langle [0,0], [1,1], [1,1] \rangle$, $1_N = \langle [1,1], [0,0], [0,0] \rangle$, $A = \langle \frac{\langle [0.1,0.4],[0.2,0.7],[0.4,0.6] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.6,0.8],[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.3] \rangle}{b} \rangle$, $B = \langle \frac{\langle [0.1,0.3],[0.3,0.8],[0.5,0.8] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.2,0.7],[0.4,0.8],[0.3,0.7] \rangle}{b} \rangle$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ is called an *IVN* topology on X .

(X, τ_N) is called an *IVNTS*.

Example 3.3 Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and the *IVN* sets are

$$C = \langle \frac{\langle [0.4,0.7],[0.5,0.7],[0.4,0.9] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.2,0.3],[0.4,0.5],[0.7,0.9] \rangle}{b} \rangle, \quad D = \langle \frac{\langle [0.5,0.8],[0.3,0.5],[0.2,0.7] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.5,0.7],[0.1,0.5],[0.3,0.7] \rangle}{b} \rangle.$$

$\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, C, D\}$ is called an *IVN* topology on X . (X, τ_N) is called an *IVN* topological space.

Theorem 3.4 Let $\{\tau_{N_i}: i \in I\}$ be a family of *IVN* topologies of *IVN* sets on X . Then $\cap_i \{\tau_{N_i}: i \in I\}$ is also an *IVN* topology of *IVN* sets on X .

Proof: (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_{N_i}$ for each $i \in I$, Hence $0_N, 1_N \in \bigcap_{i \in I} \tau_{N_i}$. (ii) Let $\{A_i: i \in I\}$ be an arbitrary family

of *IVN* sets where $A_i \in \bigcap_{i \in I} \tau_{N_i}$ for each $i \in I$. Then for each $i \in I$, $A_i \in \tau_{N_i}$ for $i \in I$ and since for

each $i \in I$, τ_{N_i} is a *IVN* topology, Therefore $\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \in \tau_{N_i}$ for each $i \in I$. Hence $\bigcup_{i \in I} A_i \in \bigcap_{i \in I} \tau_{N_i}$

But union of *IVN* topologies as seen in the following example need not be an *IVN* topology.

Example: 3.5 In example 3.2 and 3.3 the families $\tau_{N_1} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ and $\tau_{N_2} = \{0_N, 1_N, C, D\}$ are *IVN* topologies in X . For X , however their union $\tau_{N_1} \cup \tau_{N_2} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B, C, D\}$ is not a *IVN* topology.

Definition 3.6 Let (X, τ_N) be an *IVN* topological space. An *IVN* set A of X is called an interval valued neutrosophic closed set (in short *IVN* -closed set) if its complement A^c is an *IVN* open set in τ_N .

Example 3.7 Let us consider the Example 3.2, the *IVN* closed sets in (X, τ_N) are $A^c = \langle \frac{\langle [0.4,0.6],[0.3,0.8],[0.1,0.4] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.2,0.3],[0.7,0.8],[0.6,0.8] \rangle}{b} \rangle$, $B^c = \langle \frac{\langle [0.5,0.8],[0.2,0.7],[0.1,0.3] \rangle}{a}, \frac{\langle [0.3,0.7],[0.2,0.6],[0.2,0.7] \rangle}{b} \rangle$, $0_N^c = 1_N$

and $1_N^c = 0_N$ are the *IVN* - closed sets in (X, τ_N) .

Theorem 3.8 Let (X, τ_N) be an *IVN* topological space. Then (i) $0_N, 1_N$ are *IVN* - closed sets. (ii) Arbitrary intersection of *IVN* - closed sets is *IVN* - closed set. (iii) Finite union of *IVN* - closed sets is *IVN* - closed set.

Proof: (i) since $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$, $0_N^c = 1_N$ and $1_N^c = 0_N$, therefore 0_N^c and 1_N^c are *IVN* - closed sets. (ii)

Let $\{A_i: i \in I\}$ be an arbitrary family of *IVN* - closed sets in (X, τ_N) and let $A = \bigcap_{i \in I} A_i$ Now

$$A^c = \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} A_i \right)^c = \bigcup_{i \in I} (A_i)^c \text{ and } A^c \in \tau_N \text{ for each } i \in I, \text{ hence } \bigcup_{i \in I} (A_i)^c \in \tau_N, \text{ therefore } A^c \in \tau_N.$$

Thus A is an *IVN*- closed set. (iii) Let $\{A_k: k = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ be a family of *IVN* - closed set in

(X, τ_N) and let $G = \bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k$. Now $(G)^c = \left(\bigcup_{k=1}^n A_k\right)^c = \bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k^c$ and $(A_k)^c \in \tau_N$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$

, so $\bigcap_{k=1}^n A_k^c \in \tau_N$. Hence $G^c \in \tau_N$, thus G is *IVN* – closed set.

Definition 3.9 Let both (X, τ_{N_1}) and (X, τ_{N_2}) be two *IVNTS*. If each $A \in \tau_{N_2}$ implies $A \in \tau_{N_1}$, then τ_{N_1} is called interval valued neutrosophic finer topology than τ_{N_2} and τ_{N_2} is called interval valued neutrosophic coarser topology than τ_{N_1}

Example 3.10 Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and *IVN* sets are $A = \left\langle \frac{([0.5, 0.7], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.8])}{a}, \frac{([0.4, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5], [0.4, 0.7])}{b} \right\rangle$, $B = \left\langle \frac{([0.3, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.3, 0.8])}{a}, \frac{([0.1, 0.7], [0.3, 0.8], [0.2, 0.6])}{b} \right\rangle$, $C = \left\langle \frac{([0.5, 0.7], [0.3, 0.6], [0.2, 0.8])}{a}, \frac{([0.4, 0.7], [0.3, 0.5], [0.2, 0.6])}{b} \right\rangle$, $D = \left\langle \frac{([0.3, 0.7], [0.4, 0.6], [0.3, 0.8])}{a}, \frac{([0.1, 0.7], [0.3, 0.8], [0.4, 0.7])}{b} \right\rangle$. Let $\tau_{N_1} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B, C, D\}$ and $\tau_{N_2} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, C\}$ be

an *IVN* topologies on X and let (X, τ_{N_1}) and (X, τ_{N_2}) be a *IVN* topological spaces. If τ_{N_1} is *IVN* finer topology than τ_{N_2} and τ_{N_2} is *IVN* coarser topology than τ_{N_1}

Definition 3.11 Let (X, τ_N) be a *IVN* topological space. A subcollection \mathfrak{B} of τ_N is said to be base of τ_N if every element of τ_N can be expressed as the arbitray *IVN* union of some elements of \mathfrak{B} , then \mathfrak{B} is called an *IVN* basis for the *IVN* topology τ_N .

Example 3.12 In Example 3.10, for the *IVN* topology $\tau_{N_1} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B, C, D\}$. The sub collection $\mathfrak{B} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B, C\}$ of $P(X)$ is a *IVN* basis for the *IVN* topology τ_{N_1} .

Definition 3.13 Let (X, τ_N) be a *IVN* topological space and $A \in IVNs(X)$, the interior and closure of A is denoted by *IVN Int*(A) and *IVN Cl*(A) are defined as
IVN Int(A) = $\bigcup \{G \in \tau_N : G \subseteq A\}$, *IVN Cl*(A) = $\bigcap \{K \in \tau_N^c : A \subseteq K\}$

Example 3.14 Let us take an Example 3.3 and consider an *IVN* set

$E = \left\langle \frac{([0.4, 0.6], [0.4, 0.7], [0.2, 0.7])}{a}, \frac{([0.3, 0.5], [0.3, 0.6], [0.3, 0.5])}{b} \right\rangle$. Now *IVN Int*(E) = 0_N and *IVN Cl*(E) = 1_N .

Theorem 3.15 Let (X, τ_N) be a *IVN* topological space and $A, B \in IVNs(X)$ then the following properties holds:

- (i) *IVN Int*(A) $\subseteq A$
- (ii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow$ *IVN Int*(A) \subseteq *IVN Int*(B)
- (iii) *IVN Int*(A) $\in \tau_N$
- (iv) $A \in \tau_N$ iff *IVN Int*(A) = A
- (v) *IVN Int*(*IVN Int*(A)) = *IVN Int*(A)
- (vi) *IVN Int*(0_N) = 0_N , *IVN Int*(1_N) = 1_N

Proof:

- (i) Straight forward.

- (ii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow$ All of the *IVN* open sets in A that are also in B . Both *IVN* open sets included in A also included in B . *ie.*, $\{K \in \tau_N: K \subseteq A\} \subseteq \{G \in \tau_N: G \subseteq B\}$. *ie.*, $\cup \{K \in \tau_N: K \subseteq A\} \subseteq \cup \{G \in \tau_N: G \subseteq B\}$. *ie.*, $IVN Int(A) \subseteq IVNInt(B)$.
- (iii) $IVN Int(A) = \cup \{K \in \tau_N: K \subseteq A\}$. It is clear that $\cup \{K \in \tau_N: K \subseteq A\} \in \tau_N$. So, $IVN Int(A) \in \tau_N$.
- (iv) Let $A \in \tau_N$, then by(i), $IVN Int(A) \subseteq A$. Now since $A \in \tau_N$ and $IVN Int(A) \subseteq A$. Therefore $A \subseteq \cup \{G \in \tau_N: G \subseteq A\} = IVN Int(A)$, $A \subseteq IVN Int(A)$. Thus $IVN Int(A) = A$. Conversely, let $IVN Int(A) = A$. Since by (iii), $IVN Int(A) \in \tau_N$. Therefore $A \in \tau_N$.
- (v) By (iii), $IVN Int(A) \in \tau_N$. Therefore by (iv), $IVN Int(IVN Int(A)) = IVN Int(A)$.
- (vi) We know that $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$, by (iv), $IVN Int(0_N) = 0_N$, $IVN Int(1_N) = 1_N$.

Theorem 3.16 Let (X, τ_N) be a *IVNTS* and $A, B \in IVNs(X)$ then possess the following properties:

- (i) $A \subseteq IVN Cl(A)$
- (ii) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow IVN Cl(A) \subseteq IVN Cl(B)$
- (iii) $(IVN Cl(A))^c \in \tau_N$
- (iv) $A^c \in \tau_N$ iff $IVN Cl(A) = A$
- (v) $IVN Cl(IVN Cl(A)) = IVN Cl(A)$
- (vi) $IVN Cl(0_N) = 0_N$, $IVN Cl(1_N) = 1_N$

Proof:

Straight forward.

Theorem 3.17 Let (X, τ_N) be a *IVN* topological space and $A, B \in IVNs(X)$ then hold the following properties:

- (i) $IVN Int(A \cap B) = IVN Int(A) \cap IVN Int(B)$
- (ii) $IVN Int(A \cup B) \supseteq IVNInt(A) \cup IVNInt(B)$
- (iii) $IVN Cl(A \cup B) = IVN Cl(A) \cup IVNInt(B)$
- (iv) $IVN Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A) \cap IVN Int(B)$
- (v) $(IVN Int(A))^c = IVN Cl(A^c)$
- (vi) $(IVN Cl(A))^c = IVN Int(A^c)$

Proof:

- (i) By Theorem 3.15(i), $IVN Int(A) \subseteq A$ and $IVN Int(B) \subseteq B$. Thus $IVN Int(A) \cap IVN Int(B) \subseteq A \cap B$. Hence $IVN Int(A) \cap IVN Int(B) \subseteq IVNInt(A \cap B)$ -----(1)
 Again since $A \cap B \subseteq A$, by Theorem 3.15(ii). $IVN Int(A \cap B) \subseteq IVNInt(A)$. Similarly $IVN Int(A \cap B) \subseteq IVNInt(B)$.
 Hence $IVN Int(A \cap B) \subseteq IVNInt(A) \cap IVNInt(B)$ -----(2) from (1) and (2) we get, $IVN Int(A \cap B) = IVNInt(A) \cap IVN Int(B)$.
- (ii) Since $A \subseteq A \cup B$. $IVN Int(A) \subseteq IVNInt(A \cup B)$ by Theorem 3.15(ii). Similarly $IVN Int(B) \subseteq IVNInt(A \cup B)$. Hence $IVN Int(A) \cup IVN Int(B) \subseteq IVNInt(A \cup B)$.
- (iii) By Theorem 3.16(i), $A \subseteq IVN Cl(A)$ and $B \subseteq IVN Cl(B)$. Thus $A \cup B \subseteq IVN Cl(A) \cup IVNCl(B)$, $IVN Cl(A \cup B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A) \cup IVNCl(B)$ ------(1)

Again since $A \subseteq A \cup B$, by Theorem 3.16(ii). $IVN Cl(A) \subseteq IVN Cl(A \cup B)$. Similarly $IVN Cl(B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A \cup B)$. Hence $IVN Cl(A) \cup IVN Cl(B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A \cup B)$ ----- (2) from (1) and (2) we get $IVN Cl(A) \cup IVN Cl(B) = IVN Cl(A \cup B)$.

(iv) Since $A \cap B \subseteq A$, $IVN Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A)$ by Theorem 3.16(ii), Similarly, $IVN Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq IVN Cl(B)$. Hence $IVN Cl(A \cap B) \subseteq IVN Cl(A) \cap IVN Cl(B)$.

(v) $\{IVN Int(A)\}^c = [\cup \{G \in \tau_N: G \subseteq A\}]^c = \cap \{G \in \tau_N^c: A^c \subseteq G\}$,
 $\{IVN Int(A)\}^c = IVN Cl(A)^c$.

(vi) $\{IVN Cl(A)\}^c = [\cap \{G \in \tau_N^c: A^c \subseteq G\}]^c = \cup \{G \in \tau_N: G \subseteq A\}$,
 $\{IVN Cl(A)\}^c = IVN Int(A)^c$.

In theorem 3.17(ii) and (iv)), the equality does not hold. Let us display this by an example below

Example 3.18 Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and the IVN sets are $0_N = \langle \frac{[0,0],[0,0],[1,1]}{a}, \frac{[0,0],[0,0],[1,1]}{b} \rangle$;

$1_N = \langle \frac{[1,1],[0,0],[0,0]}{a}, \frac{[1,1],[0,0],[0,0]}{b} \rangle$; $A = \langle \frac{[0.1,0.4],[0.2,0.7],[0.4,0.6]}{a}, \frac{[0.6,0.8],[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.3]}{b} \rangle$;

$B = \langle \frac{[0.1,0.3],[0.3,0.8],[0.5,0.8]}{a}, \frac{[0.2,0.7],[0.4,0.8],[0.3,0.7]}{b} \rangle$, $\tau_N = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ is an IVN topology on X . Let us

consider two IVN sets $C = \langle \frac{[0.1,0.4],[0.3,0.7],[0.5,0.6]}{a}, \frac{[0.4,0.8],[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.3]}{b} \rangle$ and $D = \langle$

$\frac{[0.0,3],[0.2,0.8],[0.4,0.9]}{a}, \frac{[0.6,0.7],[0.3,0.6],[0.2,0.5]}{b} \rangle$; Now $C \cup D = \langle \frac{[0.1,0.4],[0.2,0.7],[0.4,0.6]}{a}, \frac{[0.6,0.8],[0.2,0.3],[0.2,0.3]}{b} \rangle =$

A ; $IVN Int(C \cup D) = IVN Int(A) = A$; $IVN Int(C) = 0_N$, $IVN Int(D) = 0_N$, $IVN Int(C) \cup IVN Int(D) = 0_N$;

Therefore $IVN Int(C \cup D) \neq IVN Int(C) \cup IVN Int(D)$.

By Theorem 3.17(v), $IVN Cl(C)^c = (IVN Int(C))^c = (0_N)^c = 1_N$, $IVN Cl(D)^c = (IVN Int(D))^c = (0_N)^c = 1_N$, $IVN Int(C) \cap IVN Int(D) = 1_N$; $IVN Cl(C^c \cap D^c) = IVN Cl((C \cup D)^c) = (IVN Int(C \cup D))^c = (IVN Int(A))^c = A^c$; $IVN Cl(C^c \cap D^c) \neq IVN Cl(C^c) \cup IVN Cl(D^c)$.

4. Interval Valued Neutrosophic Subspace Topology

In this section we present, along with some examples and findings, the definition of interval valued neutrosophic subspace topology.

Theorem 4.1 Let (X, τ_N) be a IVN topological space on X and $Y \in P(X)$. Then the collection $\tau_{NY} = \{Y \cap G: G \in \tau_N\}$ is a IVN topology on X .

Proof:

- (i) Since $0_N, 1_N \in \tau_N$, therefore $Y \cap 0_N = 0_N \in \tau_{NY}$ and $Y \cap 1_N = Y \in \tau_{NY}$.
- (ii) Let $Y_k \in \tau_{NY}, \forall k \in I$, then $Y_k = Y \cap G_k$ where $G_k \in \tau_N$ for each $k \in I$. Now

$$\bigcup_{k \in I} Y_k = \bigcup_{k \in I} (Y \cap G_k) = Y \cap \left(\bigcup_{k \in I} G_k \right) \in \tau_{NY}. \text{ Since } \bigcup_{k \in I} G_k \in \tau_N \text{ as each } G_k \in \tau_N.$$

- (iii) Let $Y_1, Y_2 \in \tau_{NY}$, $Y_1 = Y \cap G_1$ and $Y_2 = Y \cap G_2$ where $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$. Now $Y_1 \cap Y_2 = (Y \cap G_1) \cap (Y \cap G_2) = Y \cap (G_1 \cap G_2) \in \tau_{NY}$, since $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau_N$ as $G_1, G_2 \in \tau_N$.

Definition 4.2 Let (X, τ_N) be an *IVN* topological space on X and Y is a interval values neutrosophic subset (In short *IVN* subset) of X , the collection $\tau_{NY} = \{Y \cap G : G \in \tau_N\}$ is called interval valued neutrosophic subspace (In short *IVN* subspace) of Y . Y is called *IVN* subspace of X .

Example 4.3 Let us consider the *IVN* topology $\tau_{N_1} = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B, C, D\}$ as in Example 3.10 and an *IVN* set $Y = \langle \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.3,0.7],[0.1,0.5]}{a}, \frac{[0.5,0.9],[0.4,1],[0.2,0.6]}{b} \rangle$, $0_N = Y \cap 0_N = 0_N$;

$$G_1 = Y \cap A, G_1 = \langle \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.3,0.7],[0.2,0.8]}{a}, \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.4,1],[0.4,0.7]}{b} \rangle;$$

$$G_2 = Y \cap B, G_2 = \langle \frac{[0.3,0.6],[0.4,0.7],[0.3,0.8]}{a}, \frac{[0.1,0.7],[0.4,1],[0.2,0.6]}{b} \rangle;$$

$$G_3 = Y \cap C, G_3 = \langle \frac{[0.4,0.6],[0.3,0.7],[0.2,0.8]}{a}, \frac{[0.4,0.7],[0.4,1],[0.2,0.6]}{b} \rangle;$$

$$G_4 = Y \cap D, G_4 = \langle \frac{[0.3,0.6],[0.4,0.7],[0.3,0.8]}{a}, \frac{[0.1,0.7],[0.4,1],[0.4,0.7]}{b} \rangle;$$

Then $\tau_{NY} = \{0_N, 1_N, G_1, G_2, G_3\}$ is an *IVN* subspace topology for τ_{N_1} and τ_{NY} is called *IVN* subspace of (X, τ_{N_1}) .

Theorem 4.4 Let (X, τ_N) be an *IVN* topological space, \mathfrak{B} be an *IVN* basis for τ_N and Y is an *IVN* subset of X . Then the family $\mathfrak{B}_Y = \{Y \cap G : G \in \mathfrak{B}\}$ is an *IVN* basis for *IVN* subspace topology τ_{NY} .

Proof:

Let $U \in \tau_{NY}$ be arbitrary, then there exists an *IVN* set $G \in \tau_N$ such that $U = Y \cap G$. Since \mathfrak{B} is an *IVN* basis for τ_N , therefore there exists a sub collection $\{\chi_i : i \in I\}$ of \mathfrak{B} such that $G = \bigcup_{i \in I} \chi_i$. Now,

$$U = Y \cap G = \bigcup_{i \in I} (Y \cap \chi_i) = \bigcup_{i \in I} (Y \cap \chi_i).$$

Since $Y \cap \chi_i \in \mathfrak{B}_Y$, therefore \mathfrak{B}_Y is a *IVN* basis for an *IVN* subspace topology τ_{NY} .

5. Conclusion

The concept of interval valued neutrosophic topological space, interval valued neutrosophic interior and interval valued neutrosophic closure of an interval valued neutrosophic sets were introduced. An interval valued neutrosophic subspace topology of interval valued neutrosophic sets are also introduced. The newly introduced 'Interval Valued Neutrosophic Topological Spaces' is a stronger version of 'Neutrosophic Topological Spaces'.

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